

Including Mg I IR lines ($<7.2 \mu\text{m}$) in solar and stellar models

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Abstract

Considering the imminent launch of the James Webb Space Telescope with IR spectroscopy capabilities, our ability of calculating reliable synthetic stellar spectra in this spectral range must be improved. An important species with strong features in the spectra of late-type stars is the neutral Mg. In the present work we have improved our previous Mg I atomic model adding 128 strong transitions ($\log(gf) > -1$), up to $72\,000 \text{ \AA}$, and updated several atomic parameters. One of the most important changes is our innovative treatment of the Effective Collision Strengths (ECS) parameters, which describe excitation by collision with electrons. We employed the latest convergent close-coupling calculations (CCC) by Barklem et al. (2017) up to level 25. For transitions involving levels between 26 and 54, we compared the influence in the spectrum of two different sets of ECS parameters: the widely used combination of Seaton (1962) (for allowed transitions) plus van Regemorter (1962) (for forbidden transitions) formulas, and new ECS obtained in this work using the multi-configuration Breit–Pauli distorted-wave (DW) method. We found an overall better agreement between observed and synthetic IR spectral lines when the combination CCC and the new DW calculations for the ECS were used. This result opens the possibility of a new and more reliable approach than the formulas of Seaton and van Regemorter as methods of calculating ECS for Mg I and other species in the stellar atmospheres, when the CCC method is not available.

1 Introduction

Part of the electromagnetic radiation coming from stars that reaches our space telescopes it is absorbed or scattered by dust that interacts with visible light (Fraknoi et al. 2016). Infrared light can penetrate the dust and reveal what is hidden in other wavelengths. With the increasing detection of exoplanets, the radiation received by them from their parent star and the planet-atmosphere characterization became central aspects for habitability models.

Space telescopes missions dedicated to infrared astronomy have been providing this information by the last ~ 38 years. *Spitzer* (2003–2020) was the last operative spacecraft, preceded by *ISO* (1995–1998) and *IRAS* (1983). There is non-dedicated missions that also provided valuable IR spectroscopy data, like the Atmospheric Chemistry Experiment (*ACE*), a satellite mission on board the Canadian satellite *SciSat-1* that takes measurements of the Earth’s atmosphere. This mission provided a solar transmission spectrum in the $2.3 - 13 \mu\text{m}$ range. Another example is the *NICMOS* instrument on board of *HST*, that can observe a small portion of the infrared spectrum from 0.8 to $2.5 \mu\text{m}$, although its main capabilities resides in the UV and visible regions of the spectrum.

Lately the infrared spectroscopy is gaining attention due to the imminent launch of the James Webb Space Telescope (*JWST*). The Near InfraRed (*NIRSpec*) and the Mid InfraRed (*MIRI*) spectrographs on board of *JWST* will provide IR spectroscopy capabilities from 0.6 to $28 \mu\text{m}$. With this new and accurate information coming, our synthetic spectrum in this spectral range needs further improvement.

Neutral Mg is a relevant element not only for the Sun, its strong spectral lines, like the $3\,836.4 \text{ \AA}$ ($3p^3P - 3d^3D$) UV

transitions makes it ideal for abundance determinations in late-type and in metal-poor stars. Or the line $4\,572.4 \text{ \AA}$ ($3s^1S - 3p^3P$) that is known to have essentially an LTE source function. This line is an optically-forbidden inter-combination transition whose center is formed in the temperature minimum region, and provides a reliable source of information for the temperature of the deep chromosphere (Mauas et al. 1988). Another example is the $5\,168.8$, $5\,174.1$, $5\,185.0 \text{ \AA}$ ($3p^3P - 4s^3S$) Mg I b lines-wings, that are used as a surface gravity diagnostic in cool stars (e.g. Zhao & Gehren (2000); Fuhrmann et al. (1997)). Mg I lines are widely used to determine stellar atmosphere parameters, like the effective temperature or the gravity at the surface. For this reason, in order to study also the non-LTE (NLTE) effects it is necessary to account with accurate atomic data.

NLTE calculations for Mg I in the Sun and stars are included in recent works, like Hong et al. (2020) and the works by Alexeeva et al. (2018); Bergemann et al. (2017, 2015). There is also the series of works: Osorio et al. (2015); Osorio & Barklem (2016) and Barklem et al. (2017), among other important previous works like Scott et al. (2015); Carlsson (1992); Mauas et al. (1988). In every work it is clear that accurate Mg I atomic data is required to reproduce the observations and understand the physical processes underlying.

Osorio et al. (2015) described several studies on NLTE Mg I line formation and presented a complete Mg I atomic model. In this work they studied spectral lines in the range of $\sim 3\,800 - 8\,800 \text{ \AA}$, and included the 7.3 , 12.2 , 12.3 , 18.8 , $18.96 \mu\text{m}$ emission lines. Their computed spectra match very well the solar and five F-G-K late-type stars observations. Alexeeva et al. (2018) studied NLTE Mg I and Mg II line formation for abundance determinations in the Sun and 17 stars of

Model	Mg I levs	Mg II levs	ECS data (Mg I)	Notes
1401	26	14	SEA&VRM	Original model, Fontenla et al. (2015)
1401a	26	14	SEA&VRM	gf and broad. data updated
1401b	85	47	CCC (< lev 26) + SEA&VRM (levs 26 to 85)	gf, broad. and photoioniz. data updated
1401c	85	47	CCC (< lev 26) + DW (levs 26 to 54) + SEA&VRM (levs 55 to 85)	gf, broad. and photoioniz. data updated

Table 1: Models summary. The atmospheric model 1401 (Fontenla et al. 2015) is the same for models in this work, only the Mg I and Mg II atomic models are changed.

B-A-F-G-K spectral types. They also use spectral lines from ~ 3800 to 8800 Å, and included the lines: 7.3, 12.2, 12.3 μm . In both works, they used collision with electrons parameters produced by the R-matrix method (BSR), up to $5p^3P$ and the impact parameter method from Seaton (1962) (SEA) for transitions to Rydberg levels. Alexeeva et al. (2018) assigned an ECS equal to 1 in the case of the forbidden transitions. (Barklem et al. 2017) improved their inelastic $e+\text{Mg}$ effective collision strengths calculations, using convergent close-coupling (CCC) and the B-spline R-matrix (BSR) methods, up to the $6p^1P$ energy level.

The mentioned works do not cover spectral regions between ~ 8800 and 70000 Å. In this work we update and improve our Mg I atomic model to include transitions in the missing range. We include the latest available CCC data from Barklem et al. (2017) for the effective collision strengths (ECS) parameters, and improve it for transitions to higher levels (up to $7i^1I$) with new ECS computations. We have used a multi-configuration Breit-Pauli distorted-wave (DW) method, instead of the semi-empirical SEA formula. For transitions between levels higher than $7i^1I$, we complement with a combination of SEA, for allowed transitions, and van Regemorter (1962) (VRM) formula, when transitions are forbidden.

2 The Mg I atomic models and the NLTE calculations

We built three variants of the solar atmospheric model 1401 (Fig. 1 and Table 1), which represents the dominant feature on the solar disk at magnetic minimum (Fontenla et al. 2015). Each variant has a different Mg I atomic model, in order to detect spectra variations due to changes in atomic parameters.

Model 1401. This is our starting Mg I atomic model. It takes into account 26 energy levels (up to $3s5g^3G$) and 44 sub-levels (for quantum number J distinction). This model included 82 Mg I spectral lines in the range of 1700 - 17000 Å. The ECS parameters for excitation due to collision with electrons were obtained from the semi-empirical equations of Seaton (1962) (SEA) for allowed transitions, and from van Regemorter (1962) (VRM) when transitions were forbidden. For ionizing collisions the Allen equations in Cox (2000) were used. Photoionization cross-sections data were taken from TOPbase¹, the Opacity Project atomic database, (Cunto et al. 1993). The approximated broadening parameters values for radiative, Stark and Van der Waals, were taken from Kurucz

Figure 1: Atmospheric model 1401. Models in this work have the same atmospheric model than 1401 (Fontenla et al. 2015)

& Bell (1995)².

Model 1401a. This model also considers a 26-level Mg I atomic model, but the oscillator strengths (gf) and Einstein coefficients (A) were updated with data from NIST database (Kramida et al. 2020). The broadening data (Radiative, Stark and Van der Waals) were taken from VALD and Kurucz databases (Kupka et al. 2000; Kurucz & Bell 1995). The original ECS data from SEA+VRM were re-computed with the new transition values.

1401b and 1401c. Both models consider a Mg I atomic model of 85 levels (up to $3s20p^1P$) to reproduce in detail the mid-infrared (MIR) region. To this end, 128 Mg I strong lines ($\log_{10}(gf) > -1$), between 2770 and 72000 Å, were added to the existing 82 lines, using data from NIST database³. Levels close to the continuum (55 to 85) were added as super-levels to include the population exchange processes between higher ionized states. Photoionization parameters were updated using data from TOPbase (Cowley & Bautista 2003). These atomic models have the same updates than 1401a but the amount of levels for Mg II was also increased from 14 to 47 (up to $2p611g^2G$). Regarding excitation by collision with electrons parameters in Mg I, from level 1 to 25 ($3s6p^1P$) the latest available ECS data computed by the convergent close-

¹<http://cdsweb.u-strasbg.fr/topbase/xsections.html>

²<https://lweb.cfa.harvard.edu/amp/ampdata/kurucz23/sekur.html>

³https://physics.nist.gov/PhysRefData/ASD/lines_form.html

coupling (CCC) method (Barklem et al. 2017) were used in both models.

The most important difference between models 1401b and 1401c is the ECS data used for transitions involving levels between 26 to 54 ($3s\ 7i\ ^1I$). While model 1401b is using ECS data produced from SEA+VRM methods (from level 26 and up), 1401c uses new ECS data calculated by us through the multi-configuration Breit-Pauli distorted-wave (DW) method (using the code *AUTOSTRUCTURE*⁴ (Badnell 2011)). For a complete explanation of these calculations, see Peralta et al. (2021, in preparation). For transitions involving levels from 55 onward the ECS data were complemented with SEA+VRM.

The NLTE and synthetic spectra calculations for each atmospheric model were computed using the Solar Stellar Radiation Physical Modeling (*SSRPM*) system (Fontenla et al. 2015). The *SSRPM* solves simultaneously the radiative transfer and statistical equilibrium equations for a 1D plane-parallel atmosphere. It computes the populations of H, H-, H_2 and 52 atomic species (neutrals and the next 2 ionization states) in full NLTE with partial redistribution (PRD). It also calculates 198 species in higher ionization states using the NLTE optically thin approximation. The emergent spectrum includes 436 977 lines for atoms and ions, and 2 219 276 diatomic molecular lines in LTE.

The synthetic spectra produced by each variant is compared with IR observations from ACE-FTS Solar Atlas⁵ (Hase et al. 2010). To analyze the formation of a specific spectral line, we compare the ECS data and their effect on the populations of the levels, at the height in the atmosphere where the line is formed. To identify the formation region, we calculate the contribution function (or attenuated emissivity) of the spectral line of interest (Fontenla et al. 2007). With this information we can obtain the atmospheric parameters at those heights, such as temperature and pressure. As the ECS parameters depend on temperature, the specific values of ECS that each model is using to compute the collision with electrons are known.

3 Analysis of our results

Figure 2 shows two examples of the calculated spectral lines compared with IR ACE-FTS Solar Atlas observations. These examples are new calculations, i.e. transitions that were not included in the original atomic model of Mg I with 26 levels. Models 1401 and 1401a show no line as expected, and the spectra follows the continuum. On the other hand, models 1401b and 1401c show an acceptable match with observations.

Although models 1401b and 1401c produce deeper spectral lines than observed, model 1401c improves the match in both transitions. This improvement of model 1401c over the other models studied in this work, is found in most transitions of the IR range. This evidences that the use of the DW method for calculating ECS parameters used in 1401c model, is the reason of obtaining a better match.

The depth of a spectral line is related to the difference in populations between the transition levels, at the formation region. In order to observe in each model how different the Mg I population is re-distributed among levels, we ana-

lyzed the population ratio between models (N_{1401c}/N_{1401b}) for each level, at the average formation height. Different ECS parameters produce different collision-with-electrons transition rates, which ultimately produce a different final statistical equilibrium state. This means that population between models 1401b and 1401c changes according to the ECS data, and we should be able to detect it.

For the transitions shown in Fig. 2, we have found that the population increases up to $\sim 7\%$ in model 1401c between levels ~ 20 and 70 , at the average formation region (~ 250 km). This increase can be seen in Fig. 3, where the *models population ratio* is plotted for each level. The increase in population is driven by the DW ECS data, that is always higher than SEA+VRM data. DW parameters links Rydberg levels with lower levels (<14) using higher transition rates. This affects all transitions that have an upper level greater than 24 as a final energy state, not only the ones with the changed ECS data. The statistical equilibrium equations, as a coupled system, produce that even when the ECS parameter used for an specific transition remains unchanged, their level populations will change due to transitions involving other levels.

To illustrate the previous paragraph, for the $33\ 200.647\ \text{\AA}$ line (*left panel* in Fig. 2) the absorption occurs due to transitions from $4d\ ^3D$ (#13) to $5f\ ^3F$ (#24) terms, which use the CCC ECS data in 1401b and 1401c models. The contribution functions (Fig. 4 *left*) for these overlapping transitions, show that the formation region is approximately between 150 and 347 km, in the photosphere (Fig. 1). At these heights the population in level 13 is almost the same for both models (see Fig. 3), but for the upper-level 24 is higher in 1401c. This fact shows that using different ECS parameters in higher levels, even when the same ECS data is used for this specific transition, produces a redistribution of Mg I population among all energy levels, causing relevant changes in the spectrum.

Unlike $33\ 200.6\ \text{\AA}$ feature, transitions that produce the lines $71\ 092\ \text{\AA}$, $5f\ ^1F$ (#23) - $6g\ ^1G$ (#37), and $71\ 097\ \text{\AA}$, $5f\ ^3F$ (#24) - $6g\ ^3G$ (#38), in the *right panel* of Fig. 2 use ECS data calculated by different methods. The contribution function allows us to locate the line-forming temperatures and, therefore, the ECS data used to compute the populations. Fig. 4 (*right panel*) shows that, at the formation temperature of $71\ 097\ \text{\AA}$ feature, ECS calculated using DW method (adopted in model 1401c) is almost 3 times higher than ECS calculated using SEA method (adopted in model 1401b).

In correlation with the *models population ratio* discussed above, in general the result for an specific transition (at the line formation region) is that the *transition level ratio* (N_{low}/N_{up}) for model 1401b is usually larger than for 1401c. This is in agreement with shallower lines in the synthetic spectra of the model 1401c, and this is what we have obtained in the majority of the spectral features across the IR range, improving the match with observations.

4 Conclusions

Considering the lack in previous works of NLTE Mg I line formation studies in the IR range between $\sim 8\ 800$ and $70\ 000\ \text{\AA}$, we have proposed a new Mg I atomic model of 85 energy levels. This new atomic model allows us to reproduce spectral lines in the range of interest.

For the first 25 energy levels, the model includes the latest available data of effective collision strengths produced by the convergent close-coupling method. In order of im-

⁴<http://amdpp.phys.strath.ac.uk/autos/>

⁵<http://www.ace.uwaterloo.ca/solaratlas.php>

Figure 2: IR spectral lines. Models 1401 (blue line) and 1401a (orange dashed line) follows the continuum, 1401b (purple dash-dot line) and 1401c (red dash-dot-dot line) vs. ACE-FTS Solar Atlas observations (black dashed-line). Transitions: 33 200.6 Å (left), 71 092.0 and 71 097.4 Å (right). Although synthetic lines turned out deeper than observations, Mg I model with the CCC + DW + SEA&VRM ECS combination (1401c) produces better fits throughout the IR range studied.

proving our capacity to calculate reliable synthetic stellar spectra across a wide IR range, we compared the influence in the spectra of two different sets of ECS parameters: the widely used combination of Seaton (1962) (for allowed transitions) plus van Regemorter (1962) (for forbidden transitions) formulas, and new ECS obtained in this work. For transitions to levels up to 54 we produced new data using a multi-configuration Breit–Pauli distorted–wave method. For transitions to higher levels we employed the usual semi-

empirical formulas from Seaton (1962) and van Regemorter (1962).

We found an overall better agreement between observed and synthetic IR spectral lines, when the combination CCC and our new DW calculation for collision with electrons data were used in higher levels (model 1401c). This result opens the possibility of a new and more reliable approach than the widely used formulas of Seaton and van Regemorter, as methods of calculating ECS for Mg I (and other species) in stellar atmospheres, when the CCC method is not available.

Figure 3: Models population ratio as a function of the energy level number, at 250 km, in the photosphere. In the top of the figure, it is marked the ECS data used in each model. The up level determine the ECS data used. e.g: for transition 24–38 (71 097 Å), the SEA&VRM data is used in model 1401b (in purple) and DW data in model 1401c (in red). Mg I populations in model 1401c can be almost a $\sim 7\%$ greater than 1401b between levels ~ 20 and 70.

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Figure 4: *Left*: Contribution functions for the overlapping transitions forming the 33 200.6 Å feature, indicating that major contributions occurs at 200 - 250 km in the photosphere. *Right*: ECS data used for 71 097.4 Å line at formation temperatures. Model 1401b used SEA (purple dash-dot line) data and model 1401c the new DW calculations (red dash-dot-dot line). DW ECS data is almost 3 times higher than Sea ECS data.

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